

Microwave induced synthesis of 6-substituted-aryl-3-(4'-methyl-quinolinyl-2-oxymethyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles

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Considerable increase in the reaction rate has been observed with improved yields in the synthesis of 6-substituted-aryl-3-(4'-methyl-quinolinyl-2-oxymethyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**2a-j**) by the condensation of 1-amino-2-mercapto-5-(4'-methyl-quinolinyl-2-oxymethyl)-1,3,4-triazole (**1**) with various aromatic acid chlorides under microwave irradiation in a Maxidigest in unaltered domestic microwave oven.

In recent times there has been much interest in the use of microwave irradiation in synthesis¹ owing to substantial reduction in reaction time. Most of the reactions carried out in unaltered domestic microwave oven are either in sealed vessels or in solid phase. The substantial reduction in reaction time under microwave irradiation, the biological importance of bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles^{2,3} and our recent work on quinoline moiety⁴ prompted us to synthesise the title compounds starting from 1-amino-2-mercapto-5-(4'-methylquinolinyl-2-oxymethyl)-1,3,4-triazole.

Results and Discussion

The cyclocondensation of various aromatic acid chlorides with the bifunctional triazole (**1**) on refluxing or under microwave irradiation afforded bridgehead nitrogen

Scheme 1

heterocycles (**2a-j**) (Scheme 1). The ir spectrum of all the products showed bands at 1620–1650 cm^{-1} (C=N), and is consistent with the absence of NH_2 and SH stretching vibrations. Similarly, the absence of signals in the ^1H nmr

Table 1. Physical and ^1H nmr spectral data of compounds **2a-j***

Compd. no.	M.p. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	δ^{**}	Reaction time, h		Yield %	
			A	B	A	B
			h	min		
2a	210–12	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.7–7.7 (10H, m, ArH)	12.0	8.0	60	70
b	200–03	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)	10.0	7.0	65	73
c	290–92	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.50 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7.0–8.0 (9H, m, ArH)	8.5	6.0	75	82
d	245–47	2.30 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.7–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)	10.5	7.5	65	69
e	215–17	2.430 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)	9.0	6.5	70	80
f	285–88	1.40 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 4.20 (2H, q, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)	11.0	7.5	70	82
g	205–07	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–7.9 (9H, m, ArH)	11.0	7.0	64	75
h	280–82	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.8–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)	9.5	6.5	59	67
i	240–42	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.40 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 6.7–7.7 (9H, m, ArH)	11.5	8.0	62	72
j	298–99	2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 5.50 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 7.5–8.6 (8H, m, ArH)	8.0	6.0	68	74

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **In ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{D}_4\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$).

spectrum for the NH₂ and SH protons supports the structure. The EI-MS contains molecular ion peak at *m/z* 373 M⁺ and has 50% relative abundance value which coincide with the molecular weight of the expected product.

Based on the results, it was concluded that the reaction products are 6-substituted-aryl-3-(4'-methylquinolinyl-2-oxymethyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles. The comparison of the reaction time performed under classical heating with those performed under microwave irradiation is given in Table 1. The results demonstrate the versatility of the process as considerable reaction rate enhancement has been observed by bringing down the reaction time from hours in conventional heating to minutes with improved yields.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken on a Thomas Hoover apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 FT-IR spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on FT NMR Hitachi R 600 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS DX 303 instrument. C, H and N were analysed on a Heracus analyser. The purity of the compounds was checked on silica coated Al plates (Merck).

1-Amino-2-mercapto-5-[4'-methylquinolinyl-2-oxymethyl]-1,3,4-triazole (1): It was synthesised according to the reported method³: (yield 60%), m.p. 297–99° (Found: C, 54.48; H, 4.52; N, 24.43. C₁₃H₁₃N₅OS calcd. for: C, 54.40; H, 4.56; N, 24.40%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3250 (NH₂), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.40 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃), 4.80 (2H, br s,

NH₂), 5.40 (2H, OCH₂), 7.2–7.6 (5H, m, ArH), 13.20 (1H, s, 2-SH), *m/z* 287.

*6-Substituted-aryl-3-(4'-methylquinolinyl-2-oxymethyl)-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2a-j)*: *Method A*: To the appropriate aromatic acid (0.001 mol) dissolved in POCl₃ (10 ml), the triazole (**1**; 0.001 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 8–12 h under anhydrous condition. Excess of POCl₃ was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residual mass was poured over crushed ice and neutralised with NaHCO₃ solution. The solid thus separated was washed thoroughly with water and NaHCO₃ solution and recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (5:1).

Method B: A mixture of **1** (0.002 mol) and the appropriate aromatic acid (0.002 mol) in SOCl₂ (5 ml) was irradiated under microwave in Maxidigest for 6–8 min. After distillation of the excess SOCl₂, the residual mass was worked up as described above to yield the product.

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